

Energy consumption in wireless systems powered by RESs and equipped with UAVs and IRSs

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Agenda

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2. Considered scenario
3. Aim of the work
4. Energy models and simulation setup
5. Results
6. Conclusions

Introduction

- Increase in energy demand for the ICT sector
 - need to find alternative energy sources
- Providing reliable access to mobile services in:
 - capacity → urban areas → high network traffic
 - coverage → remote areas → lack of energy and/or telecom. infrastructure

Question: How can we face these challenges?

Proposal: The use of energy-autonomous Mobile Base Stations (MBSs)

Considered scenario

- MBS as Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)
- 2 types of the UAV:
 - fixed-wing (air-plane-like) – forward flying (10 m/s)
 - multirotor – hovering
- 2 types Renewable Energy Source (RES) generator:
 - photovoltaic (PV) panel – 1 x 20 W
 - wind turbine (WT) – 1 x 30 W
 - based on the specifications of the real devices
 - using the real weather data for Poznan (4 seasons of the year 2022)
- Additional equipment:
 - Radio Frequency (RF) Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) transceiver
 - Intelligent Reconfigurable Surface (IRS)
- Fixed network traffic:
 - 100 Mbps for Downlink (DL)
 - 50 Mbps for Uplink (UL)

Aim of the work

- Proposing complete energy models for wireless systems equipped with RESs, UAVs and IRSs
- Investigating the energy cycle characteristics for the described type of MBSs

The contribution of the paper was carried out from the ENERGY SIDE of the system

Energy models and simulation setup

Multicopter UAV

$$P_{UAV, mr}(V_{UAV}, \tilde{\kappa}) = P_0 \left(1 + \frac{3V_{UAV}^2}{\Omega^2 R^2} \right) + P_i \tilde{\kappa} \left(\sqrt{\tilde{\kappa} + \frac{V_{UAV}^4}{4v_0^4} - \frac{V_{UAV}^2}{2v_0^2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} d_0 \rho n s A_{UAV} V_{UAV}^3$$

$$P_0 = \frac{\delta}{8} \rho n s A_{UAV} \Omega^3 R^3, \quad P_i = (1+k) \sqrt{\frac{W^3}{2\rho n A_{UAV}}}, \quad v_0 = \sqrt{\frac{W}{2\rho A_{UAV}}}$$

Fixed-wing UAV

$$P_{UAV, fw}(V_{UAV}, a_{||}, a_{\perp}) = \left| c_1 V_{UAV}^3 + \frac{c_2}{V_{UAV}} \left(1 + \frac{a_{\perp}^2}{g^2} \right) + m_{over} a_{||} V_{UAV} \right| \quad c_1 = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_{D0} S, \quad c_2 \triangleq \frac{2W^2}{\pi e_0 A_R \rho S}$$

MIMO RF transceiver and IRS device

$$P_{MIMO}(M, K, T_{UL}, T_{DL}) = P_{FIX} + P_{TC}(M) + P_{CE}(M, K) + P_{C/D}(T_{UL}, T_{DL}) + P_{BH}(T_{UL}, T_{DL}) + P_{SP}(M, K) + \frac{P_{TX}}{\mu_{PA}}$$

$$P_{IRS} = N \cdot P_n(b)$$

RES generators

$$P_{PV}(\bar{G}_T, T_c) = Y_{PV} f_{PV} \left(\frac{\bar{G}_T}{\bar{G}_{T,STC}} \right) [1 + \alpha_P (T_c - T_{c,STC})]$$

$$P_{WT}(V_w) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } V_w < V_{in} \\ F(V_w), & \text{if } V_{in} \leq V_w < V_r \\ P_r, & \text{if } V_r \leq V_w \leq V_{out} \end{cases}$$

TABLE I
VALUES OF THE SIMULATION PARAMETERS [9],[11],[13],[18-23]

Symbol	Quantity	Value	Unit
m_{UAV}	mass of UAV	5.0	[kg]
m_{BATT}	mass of battery	0.94	[kg]
m_{RF}	mass of RF trans.	2.0	[kg]
m_{IRS}	mass of IRS dev.	1.0	[kg]
m_{PV}	mass of PV panel	2.78	[kg]
m_{WT}	mass of WT	6.0	[kg]
m_{PKG}	mass of addi. package	0.0	[kg]
V_{UAV}	velocity of UAV	0.0 (multicopter) 10.0 (fixed-wing)	[m/s]
$a_{ }$	forward acceleration	0.0	[m/s ²]
a_{\perp}	centripetal acceleration	0.0	[m/s ²]
g	gravita. acceleration	9.81	[m/s ²]
Ω	rotor angular velocity	300.0	[rad/s]
n	number of rotors	8	
R	rotor radius	0.15	[m]
A_{UAV}	rotor area	0.071	[m ²]
s	rotor solidity	0.067	
A_R	wing aspect ratio	118.81	
S	reference (wing) area	1.0	[m ²]
δ	profile drag coefficient	0.012	

Results – energy consumption

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Multicopter UAV:

- twice the mass → twice the energy demand

Fixed-wing UAV:

- almost no impact of the mass on the energy demand

Change in the energy demand related to the other factors (e.g., aero. forces) was omitted

Results – energy generation

Results – energy generation

PV panel:

- best season → summer
- worst season → winter

Wind turbine:

- best season → winter
- worst season → summer

Conclusions

- Ability to evaluate which configuration (UAV type and RES generator) is the best for a specific network scenario and season of the year
- Ability to evaluate the gain related to the use of RES generators for UAV-type MBSs
- Basis for planning RES-aware wireless systems
- Future work:
 - investigating the impact of other factors on the energy consumption of MBSs
 - evaluating the energy cycle for more realistic scenarios
 - taking into account the gain for wireless transmission related to the use of IRSs and MIMO transceiver

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